

An Examination of the Profile and Job Performance of the Non-Teaching Personnel in a Regional Philippine University

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Abstract:- This study examined the profile of the non-teaching personnel in Bicol University College of Education (BUCE), their level of job performance, and the strength of association between the profile and the job performance, and measures that may be proposed to sustain their performance. The study is anchored on the General System Theory of Organizations with Daft and Krepps as proponents. It made use of the descriptive correlational method with questionnaire and interview as instruments for gathering the data. It was found that a) the work assignment of the BUCE non-teaching is not proportionate to their educational qualification; b) the non-teaching personnel heads were rated outstanding by their subordinates, while the subordinates were rated very satisfactory by their heads; c) there is a moderate association between the job performance and the profile of the BUCE non-teaching personnel heads in terms of work assignment and educational qualification; while the non-teaching subordinates have a very weak correlation between the two variables which are: profile in terms of task assigned and educational qualification; and, job performance. The non-teaching personnel are highly qualified for the assigned task to them; d) The non-teaching personnel heads proposed that permanent items be given to subordinate employees; opportunities be accorded to them; financial benefits or monetary incentives will help motivate the subordinates; reclassification will elevate their status and clarify their tasks; and proper orientation and leveling of expectations be done by the heads for the subordinates' employees. On the other hand, the subordinates have proposed these measures: they be made to attend seminars and workshops; there should be equitable treatment for employees; recognition or appreciation to the efforts exerted or good performance be given/shown to them by their heads; and visibility of the heads for consultation by the subordinates is requested. Implications and recommendations are discussed.

Keywords:- Management, Job Profile, Job Performance, BUCE, Non-Teaching Personnel.

I. INTRODUCTION

In an article entitled "Trimming government bureaucracy: It's the service, stupid", Light says, "The Postal Service freeze could be easily translated into a Clinton-esque slogan" It's the service, stupid. If a job does not accelerate and improve performance, it should be cut." Such a motto requires

a deliberate implementation process, however, instead of using a freeze as the tool for flattening, the federal government must use a more deliberative process. Light further said, every supervisory layer and job has to be evaluated. If they contribute to speed and performance, they stay. If not, they go. Either the resources go back into the agency for more front-line employees, or back to the treasury for debt relief.

Light continued, "the place to start is at the very top where presidential appointees and civil service executives occupy one of the most byzantine hierarchies imaginable. Alongside eliminating bonuses and cash awards for appointees, the Obama administration might impose its own deep cuts in the 2,000 political officers appointed without Senate confirmation. A freeze on these appointments would not only save money, it would send the signal that the president means business about improving performance all the way to the bottom.

In the Philippines, "Bicol economy tops other regions in 2009", according to NSCB Region 5 Press Release. The finding is due to improved performance of the different sectors in the Bicol region. The industry sector remained the strongest performer with an 18.3 percent expansion. The improved performance of industry in 2009 further increased the sector's share to the total regional economy from 25.9 percent in 2008 to 28.4 percent in 2009. Bicol Region topped all other regions in the country in terms of growth.

Per capita Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) for the Bicol Region increase from P7,210.00 in 2008 to P7,650.00 in 2009. The 6.1 percent growth in the per capita GRDP of the Bicol Region improved the region's ranking from third lowest in 2008 to fourth lowest in 2009 among regions of the country. Industry was the largest contributor to the economic performance of Bicol Region in 2009 accounting for 4.8 percentage points of the 8.2 percent growth. Services contributed 2.2 percentage points, while the agriculture sector's share was 1.3 percentage points.

Every department or agency of the national and local governments, including state universities and colleges and government-owned and controlled corporations and even private corporations and agencies administer performance evaluation to their employees, to foster improvement of employee performance and efficiency to enhance organizational effectiveness and productivity and to provide basis for incentives and rewards, training and development, personnel actions and administrative sanctions.

The Bicol University College of Education is on the of the Teacher Training Institutions in the Philippines that was awarded the title “Center of Excellence in Teacher Education.” It is Level III Phase 2 accredited by the Association of Accredited Colleges and Universities of the Philippines (AACUP) and took active part in the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 9001:2008 evaluation whereby the Bicol University as a whole was awarded an “Institutional Certification” by TUV-SUD PSB Philippines, Inc. on January 4, 2011. There is a periodic assessment of job performance to the non-teaching personnel in Bicol University. In the College of Education, the non-teaching personnel are assessed quarterly. This quarterly evaluation is done with the goal of improving the service delivery system of the non-teaching personnel for they are the partners of the teaching personnel in the college.

It is not only the students that are evaluated or assessed in terms of their performance in their studies, but also the teaching as well as the non-teaching in terms of their specific function. The job performance evaluation or assessment is conducted to find out how far the students have learned in the different subject areas they are taking in the case of the students; while in the case of the teaching and non-teaching, the aim of evaluation or assessment is to find out how far the teaching and non-teaching employees have improved in their respective work. Without evaluation or assessment there is no challenge in doing work, there is no motivation, there is no meaning to life and there is no improvement seen on the part of the workers. However, with the assessment or evaluation of personnel in BU in particular, life on the part of the employees moves on and on,

Evaluation is carefully collecting and analyzing information in order to make decisions. There are many types of evaluations in organizations; for example, evaluation of marketing efforts, evaluation of employee performance, program evaluations, etc. Evaluation can focus on many aspects of an organization and its processes; for example, its goals, processes, outcomes, etc.

Performance reviews provide an opportunity for supervisors and their employees to regularly communicate about goals, how well those goals should be met, how well the grades are being met and what must be done to continue to meet (or change) these goals. The employee is rewarded in some form for meeting performance standards, or embarks on a development plan with the supervisor in order to improve performance.

In Bicol University, just like other institutions of higher learning, the non-teaching personnel undergo quarterly evaluation of their performance. This evaluation of performance is a system that is strengthened by performance management which included provisions for performance planning (discussion of KRA's, expectations, standards), performance review (giving feedback, coaching and counseling) the actual performance appraisal and reward management.

The performance evaluation of non-teaching personnel is governed by Executive Order No. 292 and other pertinent Civil Service Laws where Section 1 states: There shall be established performance evaluation systems in every department of agency of the national and local governments, including state universities and colleges and government-owned and controlled corporations with original charters; Section 2 states: The Performance Evaluation System or Systems shall be designed and administered to: continuously foster improvement of employee performance and efficiency; enhance organizational effectiveness and productivity; provide an objective performance rating which shall serve as basis for incentive and rewards, promotion, training and development, personnel actions and administrative sanctions; and, Section 3 (f) states: The following adjectival ratings shall be adopted: Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Unsatisfactory; and Poor. With the aforementioned, the researcher worked on this study.

II. METHODOLOGY

The study is anchored on the General Systems Theory of Organizations with Daft and Krepps as proponents. This theory presents the organization as a complex set of interdependent parts that interact to adapt a constantly changing environment in order to achieve its goals. One part of an organization is the personnel that manned the organization. Another part is the people that interact with the personnel because the people consult the personnel working in the organization for any form of transaction, just like the non-teaching personnel in Bicol University College of Education who are requested and consulted by not only the faculty members, students, but also the stakeholders and the parents of the students. Other theories that support the main theory or the General System Theory of Organization are: effectiveness theory, motivation theory, perception theory, and contingency theory. These theories described the different factors that affect the performance of organizations.

The study has conceptualized that the profile of the non-teaching personnel of Bicol University College of Education in terms of task assigned and educational qualification are related to the level of performance of the non-teaching personnel which was measured using questionnaire. The results or findings were analyzed to find out whether there is a close association between the profile and the job-performance of the personnel. The result showed the kind of relationships the two variables have. Then, the heads/supervisors and the subordinates proposed measures for the sustainability or improvement/enhancement of the job performance of the non-teaching personnel.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. The Profile of the Non-Teaching Personnel of the Bicol University College of Education

The profile of the Non-Teaching Personnel of the Bicol University College of Education is more focused on the task assigned; and, the educational qualification of the personnel. The respondents were grouped into two, namely: Personnel Heads/Supervisors, and subordinate employees. Separate questionnaires were answered by these two groups of respondents. The following tables present the BUCE Non-Teaching Personnel and their Profile.

Table 1 presents sixteen (16) non-teaching head or supervisor in Bicol University College of Education. Ten (10) of them are at the same time faculty members of the college. They are given DE loading in teaching to have time for their

office function. Only six (6) are full time heads/supervisors. More of the heads are females, only three (3) are males. On the group of the subordinates, only ten (10) are males; the rest are females. The ages of both heads and subordinates range from twenty (20) to fifty-seven (57). Of course, the subordinates are younger than the heads.

The Registrar, Supply Officer, Librarian, Administrative Officer, Accounting Officer, and Cashier are full time heads/supervisors of their office respectively. The Registrar is a very important person in the college for the office of the Registrar handles the enrolment and the records of the graduating students. With her are the office assistant. The supply officer has a very important function. He handles the office supplies, materials needed in the teaching and the office equipment to include tools and varied instrument in the subjects with laboratory like science subjects and ICT.

Table 1. Profile of the BUCE Non-Teaching Personnel Heads

Task Assigned	Educational Qualification
1. Dean of BUCE*	PhD in Filipino, EdD (Educational Mgt.)
2. Registrar	Bachelor in Elementary Education
3. Supply Officer	Bachelor of Science in Mechanical Engineering
4. Librarian	Bachelor in Library Science; MA; Licensed
5. Guidance Counselor*	EdD in Educational Management
6. Administrative Officer	BSC, LLB, MFM (Master in Financial Management)
7. Accounting Officer	BSCS w/t units in the Master's
8. BUCELS Head*	MaEd, CAR in PhD
9. BUCELHS Head*	Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)
10. Research Coordinator*	MA, CAR in PhD
11. Extension Coordinator	EdD in Educational Management
12. BAC Chairperson*	EdD in Educational Management
13. Cashier	BSBA Management
14. Experiential Learning Coordinator*	PhD (Doctor of Philosophy)
15. BUCE Graduate Program Coordinator*	PhD in Filipino
16. Information Technology Coordinator*	MA, CAR in PhD

Legend: *Faculty Member designated as head/supervisor in the study.

The Librarian has the personnel to take charge of the reference books and the different reading materials in the library of the college. The library is the heart of the college that is equipped with reading facilities like books and computers. Hence, it should be taken care of by a full-time librarian or supervisor that is competent enough to handle the functions of the library. The librarian in the college of Education is a licensed librarian and is a holder of a master's degree.

The administrative officer and the cashier take charge of the finances/funding of the college. The cashier releases the money which the personnel of the Administrative Officer have supported with the documents that the cashier is releasing. These two non-teaching personnel have very sensitive functions that without the help of their subordinate employees their offices will not function well and all the employees in the college that are both teaching and non-teaching will be affected. The administrative officer of the College of Education is a Master in Finance Management, an LLB graduate and a holder of Bachelor of Science in Commerce (BSC) with a professional civil service eligibility; while the

Cashier of the college is a BSBA major in Management holder, and is a civil service eligible. Together with the administrative officer is the accounting officer who is a holder of a BS in Computer Science and has units in the Mater's.

From the Office of the Dean, the subordinates' staff is headed by the Assistant Dean who is a Doctor of Philosophy, at the same time a faculty of the College of Education that teaches Physics and Mathematics. She acts as the OIC Dean at the time that the Dean is out of town attending seminars and conferences to represent the college. There is an information officer who is doing clerical work. She is a BEd Graduate and a civil service professional passer. With her are the equipment operator, an Administrative Aide I who has finishes a 2-year course on Automotive and Electrical Technology. He has undergone special training. Also, his partner in the Dean's Office the messenger, and Administrative Aide II, who has finished a 2-year course in accounting.

The office of the Dean has two encoders, who at the same time function as office assistants of the Dean. One is a holder of BSCS and has completed the academic requirements in MA

Eng Ed; and, the other one is a holder of Bachelor in Communication Arts, major in Audio Visual Communication and a Career Service passer. There are six (6) staff in the office of the Dean.

In the Registrar's office are two assistants at the same time encoders. One is a BEED graduate and a LET passer while the other one is a civil service eligible on Data Encoding. She is a holder of two-year course in Computer Technology. There are two student assistants in the Registrar's Office; however, they are not full-time non-teaching personnel and were excluded in the study. The Supply Office has only one (1)

office assistant at the same time encoder who helps the Supply Officer in canvassing the supplies and other materials or paraphernalia needed by the College of Education. The Supply Office assistant is a holder of a degree in Master of Arts in Public Administration (MAPA); a civil service eligible and a holder of BSBA Management baccalaureate degree.

The Cashier's Office has also one (1) office assistant at the same time encoder. She is a Bachelor of Science in Computer Science (BSCS) graduate. There are three (3) libraries in the College of Education. One is for the college, another is for the elementary, or the so-called Children's

Table 2. Profile of the BUCE Non-Teaching Personnel Subordinates

Task Assigned	Educational Qualification
A. Dean's Office	
1. Assistant Dean	Doctor of Philosophy
2. Clerk/Administrative Aide Vi	BEED Graduate; CS Professional
3. Equipment Operator/Administrative Aide I	Special Training in Automotive Technology and Electrical Technology (2-year course)
4. Messenger/Administrative Aide II	Accounting (2-year course)
5. Data Encoder/Office Assistant	BSCS; CAR in MA English Education
6. Data Encoder/Office Assistant	BCA-AVC
B. Registrar's Office	
1. Office Assistant/Encoder	CS eligible; 2-year Computer Secretarial
2. Data Encoder/Office Assistant	BEED; LET Passer
C. Supply Office	
1. Office Assistant/Encoder	CS Eligible; BSBA Management; CAR in MAPA
D. Cashier's Office	
1. Office Assistant/Encoder	BS in Computer Science (BSCS)
E. Library (College)	
1. Library Assistant/Encoder	BCA-AVC
2. Administrative Aide VI/Library Assistant	CS Professional, BSBA
3. Children's Library Assistant	BEED; LET Passer
4. High School Library Assistant	BSED Library Science
F. Guidance Office Assistant/Encoder	BSEd Biology; LET Passer
G. Administrative/Accounting Office	
1. Assistant Administrative Officer	BSC Accounting
2. HRMO Administrative Aide IV	CS Sub-Professional eligible; LET Passer; BSEd Chemistry
3. Budget Officer	AB Economics
4. Auditor	Bachelor of Science in Accountancy
5. Administrative Aide IV	BS Economics; LET Passer; CS Professional
6. Data Encoder	BS Computer Science
7. Data Encoder	MedTech Graduate
8. Laboratory Aide II	BSIE (3 rd yr)
9. Electrician (Administrative Aide IV)	BSEd Graduate
10. Physical Plant Service Aide	BS Accounting Aide (2 nd yr. college)
H. Research and Extension Office	
1. Office Assistant/Encoder	BSEd English; LET Passer
I. Bids and Awards Committee (BAC) Office	
1. Office Assistant/Data Encoder	BSCS; CS Professional
J. Experiential Learning (EL) Office	
1. Office Assistant/Encoder	BSEd Physics; LET Passer
K. Information Technology Office	
1. Office Assistant/Encoder	BS Information Technology Graduate
L. BUCELS Office of the Principal	
1. Elementary-Office Assistant/Encoder	BSBA Management

Task Assigned	Educational Qualification
M. BUCELHS Office of the Principal	
1. High School-Office Assistant	BSC
N. BUCE Graduate Program Office	
1. Office Assistant/Encoder	AB Economics

Library, and another one is the high school. However, only the library in the college has assistants. There are two (2) library assistants in college: one is a civil service professional passer, at the same time a holder of BSBA degree. The other one is a BCA-AVC holder. The High School Library is manned by a BSEd degree holder; while, the Children’s Library is taken charge of by a BEED holder and a LET passer. The Guidance Center office assistant is a holder of BSED Biology, and a LET passer.

The Administrative and Accounting Office has two groups of personnel: the administrative staff and the accounting staff. This office has two (2) heads. The subordinates of the Administrative Officer are: the assistant administrative officer, who is a BSC Accounting graduate; HRMO Administrative Aide IV, who finished BSEd chemistry, a LET passer, and a Civil Service Sub-Professional eligible; the budget officer is an AB Economics holder; an Auditor; who is a BSC graduate; and, an encoder; a clerk, who is a Med Tech graduate. The Accounting group is headed by an Accounting Officer, that is assisted by an Administrative Aide IV, who is a BS Economics graduate, a LET passer, and a CS professional passer. There is an encoder, who is a BSCS graduate. The Laboratory Aide, Electrician, an Administrative Aide IV, and, a Physical Plant Services Aide, an Administrative Aide VI who takes charge of the janitors are under the administration and supervision of the Administrative Officer. Together with the Laboratory Aide, the Physical Plant Services Aide are not college graduates, but are occupying a permanent or plantilla position and are entitled to all the benefits of a regular employee.

The Research and Extension Office has only one (1) office assistant who is a BSEd English graduate, with units in master’s degree and has a teaching load in the College of Arts and Letters. Besides, he has several years’ experience in teaching in the DepEd.

The office of the Bids and Awards Committee has one (1) office assistant. He is a BS Computer Science graduate and a Civil Professional eligible. Since the BAC has no permanent office yet, its assistant sometimes helps the Supply Officer encode documents for purchase of the materials needed by the college. A new name for the Practice Teaching Office is Experiential Learning; and, its supervisor is now named as Coordinator. The office assistant in the EI Office is a BSEd Physics graduate, and, a LET passer.

Table 3. The Sex, Position and Eligibility or License of the Heads/Supervisors

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
A. Sex		
Female	12	70.6
Male	5	29.4
Total	17	100.0
No. of Responses	6	
Total	23	
B. Position		
Data Encoder	8	50.0
Administrative Aide I	1	6.3
Administrative Aide III	1	6.3
Administrative Aide VI	4	25.0
Administrative Aide V	1	6.3
Unit Head	1	6.3
Total	16	100.0
No. of Responses	7	
C. Eligibility or License		
LET/PBET	6	66.7
CS Professional	3	3.33
Total	9	100.0
No. of Responses	14	
Total	23	

The Information Technology Office has a BS Information Technology graduate assistant. He takes charge of the Info Tech equipment and lends to the classes that are using the equipment. The Decentralized Graduate Program of BUCE has an office in the College of Education with an office assistant that is an AB Economics graduate. There are 16 offices in all that were covered by the study. The elementary and the high school laboratory schools have office assistants; however, in the high school, the office assistant seldom works in the office of the principal for he is not computer literate; but he takes charge of mimeographing or risographing test papers and works as messenger of the principal’s office. The office assistant in the office of the Elementary Principal is a BSBS Management holder.

The age and sex were looked into by the researcher that he able to get the percentage of the former and the mean of the latter. Tables 3 and 4 present the frequency and percentage of heads in terms of sex, position and eligibility or license as rated by their subordinates.

Table 4. The Sex, Position and Educational Qualification of the BUCE Non-Teaching Subordinates

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
A. Sex		
Female	7	70.0
Male	3	30.0
Total	10	100.00
No. Responses	15	
Total	25	
B. Position		
Job Order/Data Encoder	2	20.0
Admirative Aide I/ Equipment Operator	1	10.0
Administrative Aide II/Messenger	1	10.0
Administrative Aide IV	1	10.0
Administrative Aide V	1	10.0
Unit Head Assistant	2	20.0
Research Center Assistant	1	20
BUCEILS Assistant	1	10
Total	10	100
C. Educational Qualification		
Training on Automotive and Electrical Technology	1	10.0
2 nd year college (Accounting)	1	10.0
Bachelor's Degree	2	20.0
BSA-AVC	1	10.0
BEEd	1	10.0
BSEd English	1	10.0
BSBA Management	1	10.0
CAR MAEd	1	10.0
PhD in Developmental Management	1	10.0
No. of Responses	15	
Total	25	

There are more female heads than male. As far as their position is concerned, more of the heads are data encoders since it is a must that not only the subordinates should be computer literate but also the heads. In the absence of the office assistants, the heads encode the data for the office to accomplish reports and other office work on time. Four heads have the position of Administrative Aide VI; while the rest are Administrative Officers I and III. Others are Administrative Officer V and Unit Head. More of the heads are professors in the College of Education with DE loading of 3 or more teaching loads. Only a few are full-time non-teaching heads/supervisor.

As far as the heads' eligibility or license is concerned, more of them are LET/PBET passers since more of the heads are BSEd/BEEd holders in their baccalaureate degree. Only a few are civil service eligible; there were only three or 33.3%.

Data encoding for heads further means that they are the ones gathering data for their respective offices and feed those data to the college through their office. The data are made up of guidelines, policies and program of work which need to be disseminated to the faculty as well as to the students and to the college as a whole. Without these data gathered and feed by the heads to the college, the population of the college will be misguided and will be groping in the dark. The data gathering and feeding is an important function of the heads/supervisors.

On the other hands, the subordinates in every office are the support or assistants of the heads or supervisors in the encoding and in the disseminating of information or data. Table 4 present the percentage of sex, position and educational qualification of the non-teaching subordinates.

Like the heads, the non-teaching personnel subordinates are dominated by female on job order status or office assistants. Many (80%) of the subordinates are degree holders with different baccalaureate degrees. The data are based from the findings of the heads gathered by the researcher through the survey questionnaire.

B. Level of Performance of the BUCE Non-Teaching Personnel

Tables 5, 6, and 7 present the level of performance of the BUCE Non-Teaching Personnel. Table 5 presents the ages of the BUCE non-teaching personnel heads with the mean of 34.06 which means that the heads are in the prime of their working age that they are very energetic; that is why their performance is outstanding as shown in Table5. Their overall performance has the mean of 9.30 with the qualitative description of outstanding.

As far as management of work is concerned, the heads were rated outstanding (9.00) by their subordinates; so, with management of people (9.04); the courtesy and public relation of the heads were rated (9.13) outstanding; their punctuality and attendance were also rated (9.52) outstanding. Hence, the age of the heads matters a lot or affects much their job performance.

Like the heads, the subordinates non-teaching personnel of BUCE, are very energetic. With the mean rating of 38.70, the subordinate employees are enthusiastic that their overall performance is rated very satisfactory by the heads This has the mean of 8.56.

Other indicators like knowledge were rated outstanding with 9.20 mean; politeness, cordial, attentiveness was rated very satisfactory with the mean of 8.96; cleanliness, organized, orderliness was rated outstanding with the mean of 9.12; neatness and presentable appearance were rated very satisfactory with the mean of 8.75. The very satisfactory rating of the subordinates implies that they are much capable of the task assigned to them in their respective office. Also, they are highly motivated in their work that the College of Education Heads or Supervisors are helped a lot in the work.

Table 5. The Age and the Level of Performance of the BUCE Non-Teaching Personnel Heads

Indicators	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Qualitative Description
Age	16	20	57	34.06	
Overall Performance	23	8	10	9.30	Outstanding
Management of Work	22	6	10	9.00	Outstanding
Management of People	23	4	10	9.04	Outstanding
Courtesy and Public Relation	23	4	10	9.13	Outstanding
Punctuality and Attendance of Supervisor	21	8	10	9.52	Outstanding

Table 6. The Age and the Level Performance of the BUCE Non-Teaching Personnel Subordinates

Indicators	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Qualitative Description
Age	10	21	57	38.70	
Knowledge	25	6	10	9.20	Outstanding
Politeness, Cordial, Attentiveness	25	6	10	8.96	Very Satisfactory
Cleanliness, organized, orderliness	25	8	10	9.12	Outstanding
Neat and presentable appearance	24	8	10	8.75	Very Satisfactory
Overall Performance of the employees	25	8	10	8.56	Very Satisfactory

Table 7. Summary of the rating for Profile and Level of Performance of the BUCE Non-Teaching Personnel

Respondent	Sex	Age	Position	Eligibility /License	Overall Performance	Management Heads	Management Subordinates
1	1	41	2		10	6	6
2	1	51	0		10	10	10
3	0	21	0		10	10	10
4	1	29	0	2	10	10	10
5	0	23	7	2	10	10	10
6					8	8	8
7					8	8	8
8					8		8
9	0	32	4	2	2	8	8
10	0		4		10	10	10
11					8	10	10
12	0	43	4	2	8	6	4
13					10	10	10
14	0	32	0	2	10	10	10
15					8	8	10
16	0	29	0		10	8	8
17	0	27	0		10	10	10
18	0	57	5	3	10	10	10
19	1	20	0	3	10	10	10
20	1	36	1		10	10	10
21	0	27			10	8	8
22	0	22	0	2	8	8	10
23	0	55	4	3	10	10	10

As shown in table 6, the knowledge in the work together with the cleanliness, orderliness, and organization of work in the office were rated outstanding by the heads which implies that the educational qualification and values in work are commendable that these subordinates are more of assets of BUCE.

C. Strength of Association between the Profile and the Job Performance of the BUCE Non-Teaching Personnel

The profile of the non-teaching personnel of BUCE in terms of task assigned and educational qualification to include the personnel was correlated with the job performance of the BUCE non-teaching personnel. The correlation is shown in the tables that follow.

Table 8. Correlation between the Sex Profile and the Dependent Job Performance

Independent Variable: Sex	Value of Correlation	Qualitative Description
Overall Performance	.299	Weak Relationship
Management of Work	.065	Very Weak Relationship
Management of People	.054	Very Weak Relationship
Courtesy and Public relation	.299	Weak Relationship
Punctuality and Attendance of Supervisors	.134	Very Weak Relationship

Sex has a very weak relationship with the overall performance and performance indicators as shown in Table 8. The analysis indicates that it is not a good predictor of performance and can hardly be a factor to influence change in performance or of its indicators. More of the heads of the BUCE non-teaching personnel are female. Only three are males. Hence, this finding could be contributory to the very weak relationship between sex profile and job performance of the respondent heads of the non-teaching personnel in BUCE.

Age has a very weak to weak relationship with the overall performance and the performance indicators as shown in Table 9. The analysis indicates that it is not a good predictor of performance and can hardly be a factor to influence change in the performance of its indicators. The age of a supervisor can not be the only basis for measuring his performance.

Table 9. Correlation between the Age Profile and the Job Performance

Independent Variables: Age	Value of Correlation	Qualitative Description
Overall Performance	.071	Very Weak Relationship
Management of Work	-.042	Very Weak negative Relationship
Management of People	-.164	Very Weak negative Relationship
Courtesy and Public Relation	-.087	Very Weak negative Relationship
Punctuality and Attendance of Supervisor	-.029	Very Weak Relationship

Other factors may be considered. The heads of the non-teaching personnel in BUCE are the too old nor too young to hold an administrative position. It could be that they still lack experience in administrative work. The more experience a supervisor has as an administrator, the more effective he is in his work regardless of his age.

Table 10. Correlation between the Position and the Independent Variable of the Heads

Independent Variables: Age	Value of Correlation	Qualitative Description
Overall Performance	-.154	Very Weak negative Relationship
Management of Work	-.095	Very Weak negative Relationship

Management of People	-.205	Weak negative Relationship
Courtesy and Public Relation	-.226	Weak negative Relationship
Punctuality and Attendance of Supervisor	-.215	Weak negative Relationship

The position of the heads has a very weak to weak relationship with the overall performance and the performance indicators as shown in Table 10. The analysis indicates that it is not a good predictor of performance and can hardly be a factor to influence change in the performance of its indicators. It could be that the heads lack training in their designated position. Training is a very important factor in holding a position; and, becomes more effective in the application to work when combined with experience. Hence, there is a need to undergo training through attending seminar workshops and schooling in their respective position.

The eligibility or license has a moderate positive relationship with the overall performance and the indicator, management of work. The analysis indicates that the presence of an eligibility or license accounting to about fifty percent of the change, could improve performance and the maintained indicator.

Table 11. Correlation between the Independent variable and the Eligibility or License of the Non-Teaching Personnel Supervisors

Independent Variables: Eligibility or License	Value of Correlation	Qualitative Description
Overall Performance	.500	Moderate Relationship
Management of Work	.459	Moderate Relationship
Management of People	.329	Weak Relationship
Courtesy and Public Relation	.329	Weak Relationship
Punctuality and Attendance of Supervisor	.293	Weak Relationship

License for practicing one’s profession is very important, particularly for a teaching profession. The non-teaching personnel respondents in this study are the heads and subordinate non-teaching employees of the Bicol University College of Education where many of the non-teaching heads are faculty members of the college who have license and civil service eligibility and holders of the master’s and doctorate degrees. Even the full-time heads of the non-teaching

personnel have their civil service eligibility. Hence, the room for improvement in the performance of the heads is very wide.

The profile and the job performance of the non-teaching subordinates' employees were also correlated; and, the value of correlation is shown in the table that follow.

Sex has a moderate positive relationship with knowledge. The analysis indicates that it could moderately improve the knowledge of the non-teaching subordinate employees.

Many of the non-teaching subordinate employees have only meager income. Their salary is not yet to be able to meet their needs to include their professional growth. Hence, they aim for promotion and regular status to be able to augment their income and be able to grow professionally through post graduate studies and trainings. More of the non-teaching subordinates are female.

Table 12. Correlation between the Sex and Dependent Variables of the Non-Teaching Subordinates

Independent Variables: Sex	Value of Correlation	Qualitative Description
Knowledge	.429	Moderate relationship
Polite, Cordial, and Attentive	.309	Weak relationship
Cleanliness, Organization and Orderliness	.327	Weak relationship
Neat and Presentable Appearance	-.429	Moderate negative relationship
Overall Performance of the employees	.284	Weak relationship

Table 13 presents the correlation between the age and the job performance of the non-teaching subordinate employees, using the following indicators: knowledge; politeness, cordial, and attentiveness; cleanliness, organized, and orderliness; neatness and presentable appearance.

Age has a moderate positive relationship and the overall performance of the employees, which is indicative of being a good predictor of the latter. The older a person becomes, the more effective he is in his job performance; for as a person grows older, he encounters more experiences which are related or in line with his assigned task. Much more if a person is having trainings or post graduate studies that the more effective, he becomes in his work. All his experiences, trainings and studies as he grows older are useful or supportive of his work. Thus, he becomes an effective employee.

Table 13. Correlation between the Independent Variables and the Age of the Non-Teaching Subordinates

Independent Variables: Sex	Value of Correlation	Qualitative Description
Knowledge	.477	Moderate relationship
Polite, Cordial, and Attentive	-.047	Very weak negative relationship
Cleanliness, Organization and Orderliness	.062	Very weak relationship
Neat and Presentable Appearance	.360	Moderate relationship
Overall Performance of the employees	.564	Weak relationship

Table 14 shows the correlation between the position of the non-teaching subordinate personnel in their work and the independent variable with its four indicators.

Position has a moderate negative relationship with cleanliness, organization and orderliness. This indicates that the higher the position of the personnel, the less likely she/he would attend to the said factors.

Table 14. Correlation between the Independent Variable and the Position of the BUCE Non-Teaching Subordinates

Independent Variables: Position	Value of Correlation	Qualitative Description
Knowledge	-.009	Very weak negative relationship
Polite, Cordial, and Attentive	-.270	Weak negative relationship
Cleanliness, Organization and Orderliness	-.570	Moderate negative relationship
Neat and Presentable Appearance	.470	Moderate relationship
Overall Performance of the employees	.055	Very weak relationship

The educational qualification of the non-teaching subordinate is correlated to the independent variable as shown in Table 15. The independent variable has four indicators which are: 1. Knowledge; 2. Politeness, Cordial, and Attentiveness; 3. Cleanliness, Organization, and Orderliness; 4. Neatness and Presentable Appearance.

The value of correlation between the educational qualification and the performance of the non-teaching subordinate employees is -.457 which has a qualitative description of moderate relationship. This finding reveals that the task assigned to the subordinate could be done easily by the subordinates for they are educationally equipped for the assigned work.

Table 15. Correlation between the Educational Qualification of the BUCE Non-Teaching Personnel Subordinates and the independent Variable

Independent Variables: Educational Qualification	Value of Correlation	Qualitative Description
Knowledge	.208	Weak relationship
Polite, Cordial, and Attentive	.087	Very weak relationship
Cleanliness, Organization and Orderliness	-.139	Very weak negative relationship
Neat and Presentable Appearance	.138	Very weak relationship
Overall Performance of the employees	.457	Moderate relationship

The educational qualification of the BUCE non-teaching personnel subordinates has a moderate relationship with the overall performance which indicates that it is a good predictor of said variable.

Table 16 presents the correlation between the eligibility and the independent variable of the non-teaching subordinates in BUCE.

The overall performance of the employees has -.725 value of correlation, which implies that personnel with eligibility would more likely have less knowledge, be less orderly, and perform less. It could be that the feeling of the personnel is that he is safeguard by his eligibility that he is secured in his work. He could not be relieved/dismissed from the service at anytime without a substantial cause to prove the relief/dismissal. He is no longer too enthusiastic to learn more, to organize his activities, and, therefore perform less. His self-motivation has lessened.

Eligibility has a strong negative relationship with knowledge, cleanliness, and the overall performance of the BUCE non-teaching personnel subordinates. The analysis indicates that personnel with eligibility would more likely has less knowledge, be less orderly, and perform less. The reason could be that a higher portion or promotion or a regular position is being aspired for he has now an eligibility; and, the eligibility is a tool for a permanent position in the case of job orders; or, promotion in the case of those with regular position. Hence, evaluation is needed.

Table 16. Correlation between the Eligibility of the Non-Teaching Personnel Subordinates and the Independent Variable

Independent Variables: Eligibility	Value of Correlation	Qualitative Description
Knowledge	-.624	Strong negative relationship
Polite, Cordial, and Attentive	-.212	Weak relationship
Cleanliness, Organization and Orderliness	-.683	Strong negative relationship

Neat and Presentable Appearance	.312	Weak relationship
Overall Performance of the employees	-.725	Strong negative relationship

Summing up the value of correlation between the profile and the job performance/independent variable, the very weak relationship is the highest, followed by weak relationship, then moderate relationship. There is still strong negative, weak negative, very weak negative and moderately positive. Hence, the profile is not proportional to the job performance of the BUCE non-teaching personnel. There is a need for the BU administration to look into this finding in this study. Research similar to this study be conducted.

D. Measures Proposed to Sustain the Work Performance of the Non-Teaching Personnel in BUCE

The supervisors/heads as well as the subordinate employees have proposed measures to sustain the work performance of the subordinate employees in the office or in the present assignment of the non-teaching subordinate employees. These are:

On the part of the heads/supervisors, they proposed the following measures:

1. The subordinate employees be given permanent items. Their work performance shall be sustained if they will be hired on a permanent status.
2. Opportunities be accorded to them to enhance their skills and competencies.

These could be done by sending the subordinate employees to seminars/trainings.

3. Financial benefits/increase in salaries/monetary incentives will help and will encourage the subordinate employees to work better and harder.
4. Reclassification of position to qualify for promotion and increase in salary to equate the responsibility in the assigned tasks will help and will elevate the status of the non-teaching subordinate employees.
5. The functions or tasks of the subordinate employees should be made clear to them.
6. Proper orientation and leveling of expectations should be done by the heads/supervisors for the subordinate employees to be guided in the performance of the task assigned to them.

On the part of the subordinate employees, they proposed the following measures:

1. They made to attend seminar-workshops to be updated with the new or latest trends in their work assignment.
2. The supervisors/heads should have equitable treatment of employees.
3. The heads/supervisors should give recognition or show appreciation to the efforts extended or good performance of their subordinates.
4. The supervisors/heads should be visible and dedicated to their work for the subordinates to consult and be given enlightenments.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the finding of the study, the following conclusions are given: a) the work assignment of the BUCE non-teaching personnel is not proportionate to their educational qualification. They are highly qualified to the task assigned to them. There are ten (10) non-teaching personnel heads that have designations as heads/supervisor/coordinator. They are given DE loading that is equivalent to the position they are holding; b) The non-teaching personnel heads were rated outstanding by their subordinates; while the subordinates were rated satisfactory by their heads; c) there is a very weak association between the job performance and the profile of the BUCE non-teaching personnel subordinates in terms of their work assignment and educational qualification for majority of the subordinates are highly qualified for the task assigned to them. The task assigned to them is very easy for them to do. The non-teaching personnel heads are highly qualified to be in their position; hence, the relationship between their performance and their profile in terms of task assigned and educational qualification is only moderate; d) there were six (6) measures proposed by the non-teaching personnel; and, four (4) measures proposed by the non-teaching subordinates to sustain their work performance. The six from the heads are: permanent items be given to subordinate employee; opportunities be accorded to them; financial benefits or monetary incentives will help and will motivate the subordinates; reclassification will elevate their status and clarify their task; and, proper orientation and leveling expectations be done by the heads for the subordinate employees. On the other hand, the subordinates have proposed these measures: they be made to attend seminars and workshops; equitable treatment of employees; recognition or appreciation to the efforts exerted or good performance be given/shown to them by their heads; the visibility of the heads for consultation by the subordinates is requested.

Based on the conclusion given, the following recommendations are presented: a) the BUCE non-teaching subordinate employees that are on job order status be considered for permanent position; so, their salary will increase and they could enroll in the Graduate School for professional growth; b) the BUCE non-teaching personnel should maintain the outstanding rating for the heads, and very satisfactory rating for the subordinates; c) they should be motivated through promotion and conversion to permanent/regular status for those that are not yet on permanent/regular status; so, they would work harder; d) they should be assigned task that is proportionate to their field of specialization or degree earned/finished; e) the proposed measures be given action by the administrators of Bicol University through the recommendation of the Dean of the College of Education; f) more researches along this subject of study be conducted by other researchers.

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